

DEVELOPMENT OF EXPLOSIVE ABILITY IN SCHOOLCHILDREN (on the example of 10-11 grades)

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the study of the dynamics of the development of explosive motor skills in schoolchildren by grades. Based on their experimental research, the authors highlighted the advantages of the SPORK device in the development of explosive motor skills in girls, boys and schoolchildren of 10th and 11th grades engaged in sports of the same age.

Relevance. Much attention in our country is paid to the development of physical culture and mass sports. If we talk about the development of mass sports, first of all, it is necessary to form the interest and motivation of school-age children in sports. In this regard, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 3, 2017 No. PP-3031, decisions on measures for the further development of physical culture and mass sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan will become the basis for the further development of mass sports in our country.

The growth of success in sports always requires a new level of development of physical capabilities from the athlete. At the same time, it is necessary to increase the training and competitive load. It is desirable to create modern, convenient, efficient technologies to facilitate loading. In order to master and

improve each sport, it is necessary to develop the skills associated with that same sport. If skills development begins at school age, it will be easier to achieve high results in the future. Measuring the explosive mobility of high school students and studying their various results is one of the most pressing problems today.

The purpose of the study: to study the dynamics of the explosive ability of schoolchildren in grades 10-11.

Organization of the study: In our study, the city of Chirchik.

It was attended by 42 students of secondary school No. 13, including 18 school-age students involved in physical education, and 24 students who are not involved in sports. In general, there is an increase in the indicators of the explosive ability of schoolchildren from class to class. At the same time, there is a significant difference in the growth of the results of boys and girls involved in sports, and those

who do not. This can be seen from the results obtained in the experiment. In 11th grade, there is a significant increase in

explosive motor skills in boys and girls compared to 10th grade, see Figure 1

Figure 1. Dynamic indicators of students' explosive ability

As can be seen from the figure, as the number of classes increases, so does the growth dynamics of this ability, i.e., the significance level was found between boys and girls, between sports and non-sports sports, between each class ($P < 0.01$ to $P < 0.001$). At the same time, the performance of students involved in sports is higher than the performance of students enrolled in the state program ($P < 0.001$). The results show the uniqueness of the SPORK and the high degree of stratification.

The advantage of the style is that the SPORK device allows you to quickly develop explosive mobility, versatility, low power and time to achieve high results, no injuries, the ability to use in different places, convenience, the ability to develop this ability on your own, economically,

does not require large amounts of money, does not take up much space in the gym.

Special requirements for newly developed methods in experiments are: high differentiating power, scientific validity and reliability, objectivity, reliability and stability of the result, uniqueness and stratification, adequacy (similarity) of quality, compatibility of pedagogical observations with the results obtained. Benefits and Communication with practice has been confirmed by the created technology. (Gapparov Z.G., Ishtaev Zh.M., Ishtaev D.R., Kholmurodov L.Z.)

Scientific validity and reliability of the new method. The SPORK apparatus was developed by L.P. Matveev, Yu.V. Verkhoshansky, R.A. Akramov, F.A. Kerimov, R.E. Nurimov and other scientists. Creation of special methods for successful development and theory of abilities I.M.

Sechenov, S.L. Rubinstein, A.R. Luria, B.M. Teplova, V.D. Shadrikov, mechanisms of conscious motion control by O.A. Konopkina, The theory of installations by N. Uznadze and the concept of the importance of re-information are taken as the basis.

The essence of this method is that during a training exercise with a vertical jump, a goal is set and each time the jump is re-informed. When the goal is not achieved, the athlete corrects his actions. An increase in the ability to explosive movements was noted when performing jumping exercises 3 times a day. Therefore, our proposal would be appropriate if instead of the school norm of high jumps, the vertical jump exercise was used. This is because the ability for explosive movement increases dramatically as a result of jumping. High results can be achieved if the SPORK instrument, designed for measurement and teaching, is multiplied and distributed in schools.

Scientific research methods or appropriate tests used in the field of sports psychology have specific advantages, and in studying the psychosomatic function of an individual, it is very important to take into account their proportionality, reliability and informational values. At the same time, due to the emergence of new problems, scientific ideas and theoretical hypotheses, it is natural that these methods and tests are constantly being improved. The SPORK measuring device developed by the authors of the article is designed to determine the rate of explosive force associated with jumping vertically.

This device, which has been tested on the basis of long-term experimental studies, has been shown to have a number of metrological advantages over the

Abalakov device used in sports practice in determining the level of explosive force associated with vertical jumping. In particular, the indicators of "vertical jump-explosive force" obtained during the use of the device "SPORK" and its experimental testing can serve as an objective and reliable criterion in psychodiagnostic and prognostic aspects.

It is known that when determining the speed of jumping in the vertical direction using the Abalakov method, a simple "tape-meter" moving from the "rubber bucket slit" is attached to the belt attached to the subject's waist and the number is determined while standing. Upon instruction, the subject jumps vertically from his or her position using an active arc motion and lands in place. The jump height is then measured by a moving meter during the jump. Apparently, the examinee is not able to observe his own result and is unaware of it during the performance of the test. This means that the subject has almost no motivation to jump. Satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the result will appear at the end of the test.

When jumping with the help of the device "SPORK", on the contrary, the examinee in his mind creates an idea of the order of jumping, its elements, flexion and extension of the legs, inertial movement of the hands, visually observes the result. Such a situation raises the emotional tone of the subject, in which a feeling of activity and curiosity arises. Consequently, the reaction of the motivational installation, which satisfies the need to jump and demonstrate maximum explosive power, increases. It is these factors that mobilize the maximum explosive force to achieve a high jump result.

In a word, the vertical jump on the SPORK apparatus serves to sharply increase the explosive ability of schoolchildren in sports. This, in turn, makes it easier to master sports that require fast strength.

In the SPORK device, the development of explosive abilities of students by age, weight and gender does not matter..

In this device, students do not have the possibility of getting injured and have the ability to predict the outcome of the competition by jumping before the competition.

Each student included psychological factors such as getting quick information after jumping on the SPORK device, setting a goal before jumping, concentrating the will to reach the goal, and increasing motivation after reaching the goal.

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